

1 **IRX transcription factors function in transformation and metastasis through a steroidogenic**
2 **mechanism.**

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7 We studied IRX transcription factor function in a variety of biologic contexts. IRX3 was modulated at
8 multiple points during melanoma progression, together with a network of genes functioning in steroid
9 metabolism; those genes included ACSL1, HSD11B2 and SRD5A1. IRX co-regulation indicated control of
10 the androgen receptor (AR) by IRX3. In addition to requirements for IRX transcription factor activity for
11 invasive disease processes like lymph node metastasis during the course of metastasis to the CNS,
12 changes in IRX expression appeared important during the course of general transformation in vitro, where
13 it transcriptionally interacted with FGFR2/3 and was associated with resistance to growth factor inhibition,
14 expression of p53 targets and an oncogenic Ras gene signature. Gene Ontology (GO) analysis indicated
15 a function for IRX transcription factors in stem cell differentiation, development and maintenance (GO BP),
16 in addition to development of multicellular organisms and organ and cell morphogenesis, indicating IRX
17 influence with organ system signaling likely through regulation of Wnt and Hippo pathways, supporting a
18 function for the IRX factors as primary mediators of metastasis to distant organ sites through steroidogenic
19 invasiveness and metastasis to the lymph nodes.
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